

СОЯЛП АЛПЕР АХМЕТ,

*студент (Туреччина) кафедри іноземних мов та міжкультурної комунікації,
факультет підготовки іноземних громадян, ХНЕУ імені Семена Кузнеця.
Науковий керівник: Михайлюк Н.В., ст. викл. кафедри іноземних мов та
міжкультурної комунікації, факультет підготовки іноземних громадян,
ХНЕУ імені Семена Кузнеця*

**ADAPTATION OF FOREIGN STUDENTS TO UKRAINIAN
EDUCATIONAL STANDARDS**

Before we focus on the adaptation process, we need to study these two points together;

1-The foreign students; characters, skills, immediate goals, dreams, needs and the reason to choose Ukraine.

2- Ukrainian educational system;

-what are the key points of this system?

How can this system take a student from abroad?

In which way does it develop students?

Foreign students usually come from these countries; Turkey, Azerbaijan and Asia- Turkey countries, India, China, Cameroon, Nigeria, Morocco and Arab countries.

The major point of the system is method of accepting students. If we compare with the other countries, it is very easy. Almost there is no requirements. It is good to be competitive, but unfortunately the foreign students who study in Ukraine, they are in the lowest succeeding zone according to their home country success ranking.

To work with this zone, it is necessary to have something different.

Current system has enough ability to manage this situation, but success ratio needs to be increased. And also we can easily say that. Everybody can have success with high standards. The important and difficult point is, to catch a success with low standards. With this, there will be a really working system and after that the system will be more competitive and then, it will be strong brand in education world.

The reasons of the students, to study in Ukraine;

-To have real and good education

To live or work in Russian speaking countries

-To learn foreign language

To see foreign country

-Easy to say that 'I am university student'

- Escape from military training
- To transfer to their home country universities

Common problems of foreign students:

- Language problems
- Not enough pre-university course skills

Language adaptation to education (English, Russian, Ukrainian is not a mother tongue for them)

- New city life adaptation
- Too much freedom (not enough family control)
- Very big difference between Ukraine educational system and their home country system
- There is no adviser to manage the situation

Preparatory department is the most important point for this adaptation. With this department adaptation issue can be sorted out properly. And also for some students, there should be an opportunity to jump over this prep-class and to start the university at once. This opportunity should be given with not only course and language exam. Another type of exam should be applied, for example student mental exam.

In prep class it is not a good idea to collect the students of the same nationality in one class. And also it is not a good idea to make a random nationality class. The best idea is to make class according to student mental report with the course-language skill levels.

This system provides its own standards by teacher's action. In this system, student- teacher relationship is so close and strong. Teachers can decide and control almost everything on student's marks and student's performance. So it means that, this is teacher-based standard system. With this type system, teachers can perform good results with only small classes in which there are no more than 8 students.

АДАПТАЦІЯ СТУДЕНТІВ-ІНОЗЕМЦІВ ДО УКРАЇНСЬКИХ ОСВІТНІХ СТАНДАРТІВ

Кожного року багато іноземних студентів приїжджає до України, щоб навчатися в українських університетах та отримати вищу освіту. Це важливо як і для самих студентів, так і для розвитку української системи освіти у сфері конкурентоспроможності на ринку освітніх послуг. В тезах розглядається питання адаптації іноземних студентів з соціальної точки зору. Піднімається питання причин навчання іноземних студентів саме в українських закладах вищої освіти, розкриваються питання труднощів, з

якими стикаються студенти в процесі адаптації до нового життя з психологічного та педагогічного погляду.

Ключові слова: процес адаптації, високі стандарти, мовна адаптація, підготовче відділення.

ALPER AHMET SOYALP ADAPTATION OF FOREIGN STUDENTS TO UKRAINIAN EDUCATIONAL STANDARDS

Every year, many foreign students come to Ukraine to study at Ukrainian universities and get higher education. This is important both for the students themselves and for the development of the Ukrainian education system in the field of competitiveness in the market of educational services. Theses consider the issue of adaptation of foreign students from a social point of view. The question of the reasons for the study of foreign students in Ukrainian higher education institutions is raised, the issues of difficulties faced by students in the process of adaptation to a new life from a psychological and pedagogical point of view are revealed.

Key words: adaptation process, high standards, language adaptation, preparatory department.